

CALCULATION OF EFFECTIVE MODULI OF VISCOELASTIC COMPOSITES WITH PERIODIC MICROSTRUCTURES USING A HOMOGENIZATION METHOD

Yeong-Moo Yi, Sang-Hoon Park and Sung-Kie Youn

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology, 373-1, Guseong-dong, Yuseong-gu, Taejeon, 305-701, Korea

SUMMARY: For composites with viscoelastic material phases, a systematic way of calculating the effective viscoelastic moduli in time domain is developed. With the effective moduli in time domain, effective complex moduli in frequency domain are obtained by using the Fourier transformation. The problem of calculating the effective moduli of general viscoelastic composites is formulated using the asymptotic homogenization method. The memory effects due to the homogenization are presented in general form and a sufficient condition for the effects to disappear is discussed. The effective relaxation moduli are calculated in Laplace transformed domain and are numerically inverse-transformed into time domain. Numerical examples are presented to illustrate and verify present approach and to discuss the memory effects. Results show that due to the presence of memory effects, additional terms are required for the accurate inverse Laplace transformation in the Prony series approximation of the homogenized relaxation moduli.

KEY WORDS: effective moduli, viscoelastic, homogenization, memory effects.

INTRODUCTION

The behavior of the composite materials is highly complex and the characterization of the constitutive behavior is important for accurate analysis of composite structures. But it is almost impossible to analyze the composite structures on the microscopic level by considering the heterogeneity of composite materials. There are several different approaches to obtain the macroscopic properties of such composites. Among many other methods of obtaining the effective moduli, the asymptotic homogenization method[1,2] has several attractive features mainly due to its systematic mathematical approach. Hollister and Kikuchi [3,4] showed that the homogenization method gave better estimations of the effective elastic moduli of composites than standard mechanics approaches.

Although Sanchez-Palencia [1] and Suquet [5] have dealt with the problems for the simple cases of the Voigt model and the Maxwell model, respectively, in viscoelastic composites, the discussions on the estimation of the effective relaxation moduli or the effective creep compliances of general viscoelastic composites in time domain are rarely found.

EFFECTIVE VISCOELASTIC MODULI BY A HOMOGENIZATION METHOD

A heterogeneous medium with a periodic structure may be replaced by an effective homogeneous one when the period is very small compared to the global length scale. In the homogenization method, the field variables are assumed to vary in the multiple scales, i.e., in the local and global scales and they are represented by asymptotic expansions in each spatial scale. Due to the periodicity of the microstructure, field variables such as displacement, strain, and stress are assumed to be periodic with respect to the local scale. The effective moduli are then obtained by investigating the asymptotic behavior of the medium as the period of the microstructure goes to zero.

Derivation of the Homogenized Moduli

To deal with two different length scales associated with the microscopic and the macroscopic behaviors, the global coordinate is designated by \mathbf{x} and the local coordinate by \mathbf{y} . The global coordinate and the local coordinate are related with each other by a positive real parameter ε as follows.

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x} / \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

For the averaging process of the homogenization, the mean operator, $\tilde{\cdot}$, on Y is defined as follows. $|Y|$ is the measure of Y .

$$\tilde{\bullet} = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y \bullet \, dy \quad (2)$$

The following problem of viscoelastic composites with a periodic microstructure is considered, where the inertia effects and the body forces are not present.

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (3)$$

$$u_i^\varepsilon = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial_1 \Omega, \quad \sigma_{ij}^\varepsilon n_j = F_i \quad \text{on } \partial_2 \Omega \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int_0^t G_{ijkl}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t - \tau) \frac{\partial e_{kl}(\mathbf{u}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \tau))}{\partial \tau} d\tau \quad (5)$$

where Ω is an open connected domain, $\partial_1 \Omega$ the displacement-prescribed boundary, $\partial_2 \Omega$ the traction-prescribed boundary, and F_i the traction force on $\partial_2 \Omega$. $G_{ijkl}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is relaxation tensor.

Since $G_{ijkl}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is dependent on ε , $u_i^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x})$ is also dependent on ε . The asymptotic behavior is to be observed as ε goes to zero. $u_i^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t)$ has an asymptotic expansion as follows.

$$u_i^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t) = u_i^0(\mathbf{x}, t) + \varepsilon u_i^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \varepsilon^2 u_i^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \dots; \quad \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x} / \varepsilon \quad (6)$$

where $u_i^m(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ is Y -periodic in \mathbf{y} and is independent of ε . The asymptotic expansions for e_{ij}^ε and σ_{ij}^ε are obtained as follows.

$$e_{ij}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t) = e_{ij}(\mathbf{u}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t)) = e_{ij}^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \varepsilon e_{ij}^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \dots ; \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x} / \varepsilon \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sigma_{ij}^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \varepsilon \sigma_{ij}^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \dots ; \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x} / \varepsilon \quad (8)$$

$$e_{ij}^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = e_{ijx}(\mathbf{u}^0) + e_{ijy}(\mathbf{u}^1) \quad (9a)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = \int_0^t G_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, t - \tau) \frac{\partial e_{kl}^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \quad (9b)$$

In (9) the subscripts x and y mean the differentiation with respect to x_i and y_i , respectively.

By introducing (8) into (3), arranging it against ε^{-1} and ε^0 , applying the mean operator, we obtain following two equations.

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial y_j} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^0(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad (11)$$

Equations (10) and (11) represent the local and the global problems, respectively. By solving the local problem (10), the homogenized viscoelastic moduli can be obtained. Applying Laplace transformation to (10), the local problem becomes

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial y_j} \left[s \hat{G}_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, s) e_{kly}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, s)) \right] = e_{klx}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}^0(\mathbf{x}, s)) \frac{\partial (s \hat{G}_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, s))}{\partial y_j} \quad (12)$$

where variables with \wedge indicate that they are Laplace transformed. Then the following variational formulation of the local problem is obtained in Laplace transformed domain.

Find $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, s)$ such that

$$\int_Y s \hat{G}_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, s) e_{kly}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, s)) e_{ijy}(\mathbf{v}) dy = -e_{klx}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}^0(\mathbf{x}, s)) \int_Y s \hat{G}_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, s) e_{ijy}(\mathbf{v}) dy \quad (13)$$

In (13), when $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^0$ is given, $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^1$ can be obtained in terms of $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^0$. To treat this problem, we define a space with the associated inner product as follows.

$$\tilde{V}_Y = \{ \mathbf{u} \in V_Y \mid \tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{0} \} \quad (14)$$

$$(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})_{\tilde{V}_Y} = \int_Y s \hat{G}_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}) e_{kly}(\mathbf{u}) e_{ijy}(\mathbf{v}) dy \quad (15)$$

$$(\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}(s), \mathbf{v})_{\tilde{V}_Y} = \int_Y s \hat{G}_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, s) e_{ijy}(\mathbf{v}) dy, \quad \forall \mathbf{v} \in \tilde{V}_Y \quad (16)$$

Then (13) becomes

$$(e_{klx}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}^0(\mathbf{x}, s)) \hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, s) + \hat{\mathbf{u}}^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, s), \mathbf{v})_{\tilde{V}_Y} = 0, \quad \forall \mathbf{v} \in \tilde{V}_Y \quad (17)$$

Therefore, $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^1$ is given in terms of $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^0$ and $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}$ as follows.

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}}^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, s) = -e_{klx}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}^0(\mathbf{x}, s))\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, s) + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}, s) \quad (18)$$

By applying inverse Laplace transform to (18), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij}^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = & \int_0^t G_{ijkl}(y, t - \tau) \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \left[e_{klx}(\mathbf{u}^0(\mathbf{x}, \tau)) \right. \\ & \left. - \int_0^\tau e_{mnx}(\mathbf{u}^0(\mathbf{x}, \tau)(\tau - p)) e_{kly}(\mathbf{w}_{mn}(\mathbf{y}, \tau)(p)) dp \right] d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

By using the Leibnitz rule, by changing the order of the double integration, and by applying the mean operator, the homogenized stress-strain relations are obtained as follows.

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^0(t) = \int_0^t G_{ijkl}^h(t - \tau) \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} e_{klx}(\mathbf{u}^0(\mathbf{x}, \tau)) d\tau \quad (20)$$

where the homogenized viscoelastic relaxation modulus, G_{ijkl}^h , is given as follows.

$$G_{ijkl}^h(t) = \left[G_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, t) - \int_0^t G_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}, t - p) e_{mny}(\mathbf{w}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, p)) dp \right] \tilde{\quad} \quad (21)$$

Consequently, when the original moduli are replaced by the corresponding homogenized ones, the homogenized problem has exactly the same form as the original problem defined by equations (3),(4) and (5).

Calculation of the Effective Relaxation Moduli

By taking Laplace transformation of (21), we obtain

$$s\hat{G}_{ijkl}^h(s) = \left\{ s\hat{G}_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}, s) \left[\delta_{mk} \delta_{nl} - e_{mny}(\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, s)) \right] \right\} \tilde{\quad} \quad (22)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, s)$ is the solution of the following local problem in Laplace transformed domain.

$$\int_Y s\hat{G}_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}, s) e_{mny}(\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, s)) e_{ijy}(\mathbf{v}) dy = \int_Y s\hat{G}_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, s) e_{ijy}(\mathbf{v}) dy, \quad \forall \mathbf{v} \in \tilde{V}_Y \quad (23)$$

$G_{ijkl}^h(t)$ can be obtained from inverse Laplace transformation of $\hat{G}_{ijkl}^h(s)$ which is obtained from (22). Note that (23) has nearly the same form as the typical elastostatic problems. The right-hand side of (23) acts like body forces. The boundary conditions are specified in the form of periodic boundary conditions on $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}$. The homogenized elastic moduli can be calculated by the finite element codes with slight modifications.

MEMORY EFFECTS

In addition to the original memories of the constituent materials of viscoelastic composites, the homogenization process induces the additional long-term memories. This behavior is termed as the memory effects. Sanchez-Palencia[1] and Suquet[5] showed that the long-term memory appeared as a result of homogenization for composites in which the viscoelastic phase is treated with a Voigt model or a Maxwell model. In the following, the memory effects are discussed in the general form.

Memory Effects

The integral term in (21) represents the memory effects. It can be seen that the homogenized relaxation moduli depend on the history of the relaxation moduli of the constituent materials as well as on the current value of the moduli. If the relaxation moduli $G_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, t)$ is separable with respect to space and time, the memory effects do not appear. If $G_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, t)$ is separable in \mathbf{y} and t , Laplace transform of $G_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, t)$ is given by

$$s\hat{G}_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, s) = sF_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y})\hat{T}(s) \quad (24)$$

Plugging (24) into (23), the following local problem is obtained.

$$s\hat{T}(s) \int_Y F_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}) e_{mny}(\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}) e_{ijy}(\mathbf{v}) dy = s\hat{T}(s) \int_Y F_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}) e_{ijy}(\mathbf{v}) dy, \quad \forall \mathbf{v} \in \tilde{V}_Y \quad (25)$$

From (25), it is evident that $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}$ is not a function of s . Thus from (22), we obtain

$$s\hat{G}_{ijkl}^h(s) = \left\{ s\hat{T}(s) F_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}) \left[\delta_{mk} \delta_{nl} - e_{mny}(\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{kl}(\mathbf{y})) \right] \right\}^{\sim} = s\hat{T}(s) F_{ijkl}^h \quad (26-a)$$

$$G_{ijkl}^h(t) = F_{ijkl}^h T(t) \quad (26-b)$$

From the above results, it can be seen that the memory effects come from the coupling effects of the spatial and the temporal variations of the viscoelastic moduli. The memory effects make the homogenization problem complicated. It is required to solve the local problem for every s if the relaxation moduli are not separable with respect to space and time variables, while it is sufficient to solve the local problem only once when the relaxation moduli are separable as can be seen in [25].

Inverse Laplace Transformation

Since the homogenized relaxation moduli are calculated in Laplace transformed domain, inverse Laplace transformation is required if the memory effects appear. In the present work, the least-square fitting in Laplace transformed domain is employed based on the Prony series representations of the relaxation moduli. Since it is difficult to optimize the relaxation times of the fitting function because of its nonlinear behavior, the relaxation times should be properly chosen in the region where the relaxation curve changes rapidly [6]. Because of memory effects, more terms in the Prony series are required in the fitting function than the number of terms in the Prony series representations. Once the approximations are made in the

Laplace transformed domain, the relaxation moduli in time domain and the complex moduli as well as the loss tangent in frequency domain are readily obtained using the known relations [7].

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSIONS

Numerical examples are presented to discuss the memory effects and their applications. In the following examples, two dimensional plane stress states is considered and the constituent materials are assumed isotropic.

As a first example, in order to observe the memory effects, a viscoelastic composite with the elastic circular inclusions in the viscoelastic matrix in which the stiffness of the elastic inclusions is comparable to that of the viscoelastic matrix is treated. The moduli and Poisson's ratio of the elastic inclusions are

$$E = 20, \quad \nu = 0.21 \quad (27)$$

The moduli of the viscoelastic matrix, which are represented by using the standard linear solid model [7], are given by

$$E(t) = 3 + 17e^{-t}, \quad \nu = 0.38 \quad (28)$$

The volume fraction of the inclusions is 40%. Due to the presence of the long term memory effects, the homogenized relaxation moduli cannot be represented exactly with the standard linear solid model. It is, therefore, required to introduce additional terms in the Prony series representation. To see the effect of the number of the terms in the Prony series approximations, the number of relaxation terms (N_f) is varied by 1, 3, 5, and 7. Figure 1 shows the results. They show that small errors introduced in the Prony series approximations of the homogenized relaxation moduli in Laplace transformed domain may cause large errors in converting the data into those of time and frequency domains.

As a second example, composites with the microstructure composed of two isotropic viscoelastic materials with different relaxation times are used. The relaxation moduli are given as follows.

$$E(t) = 3 + 17e^{-t/10}, \nu = 0.38 \text{ for material 1} \quad (29)$$

$$E(t) = 3 + 17e^{-t}, \nu = 0.38 \text{ for material 2} \quad (30)$$

The effective moduli of the two composites are calculated. In the first composite, material 1 is used as the circular inclusion and material 2 as the matrix, and in the second one, the roles of material 1 and 2 are interchanged. The volume fractions of material 1 and 2 are the same in both composites, i.e., 50%, respectively. Figure 2 shows the calculated results. The results show that the loss tangents and thus the damping effects of the homogenized materials as a function of frequency can be significantly affected by the configurations of the microstructure as well as the relaxation moduli of the constituent materials. Also figure 2 (c) shows that we may be able to get the increased damping effect in a certain desired frequency interval by fabricating the composites, which has a special microstructural configuration, of two or more viscoelastic materials even if each of the constituent material has low damping effect in that frequency interval.

CONCLUSIONS

A systematic way of calculating the effective or homogenized relaxation moduli of the general linear viscoelastic composite materials in time domain is developed by using a homogenization method. The memory effects due to homogenization have been presented in general form and it has been shown that the memory effects disappear if the relaxation moduli are separable in space and time. The memory effects make the numerical inverse Laplace transformation very complicated.

The memory effects and inverse Laplace transformation are discussed in detail. Due to the presence of the memory effects, in the Prony series approximation of the homogenized relaxation moduli, the additional terms are required for the accurate inverse Laplace transformation. It is also shown in the numerical example that maximum damping can be achieved by choosing specific configuration of the microstructures of the composites.

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(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 1: Effect of number of fitting terms; a) effective modulus in Laplace transformed domain, b) effective modulus in time domain and c) effective loss tangent in frequency domain.

Fig. 2: Composite of two viscoelastic materials; a) effective modulus in Laplace transformed domain, b) effective modulus in time domain and c) effective loss tangent in frequency domain.